

Harnessing Social Media Activism: A Focus on Youth Commitment to Development in Delta State, Nigeria

Annmarie Nkem Okoli, Ph.D.

Department of Sociology/Criminology, Dennis Osadebey University, Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria

Edafe Ulo

Department of Sociology/Criminology, Dennis Osadebey University, Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria

Abstract

As Delta State grapples with a myriad of developmental problems such as poverty, unemployment, inequality, inadequate infrastructure and political instability, among others, the utilization of social media as an effective tool for youth activism and engagement has become inevitable. Hence, this study investigated how harnessing social media activism can foster youth commitment to development in the State. Three research objectives were outlined in the study and were anchored on the Technological Frame of Reference theory. A sample size of 392 respondents was selected from Asaba Metropolis through the purposive sampling technique. The data collection process utilized a structured questionnaire to gather data from respondents. The analytical approach employed frequency distribution tables, simple percentages, arithmetic mean and standard deviation. The analysis indicated that the youth actively use Face book, X, Instagram and YouTube, among others for social media activism, social media activism has impacted youth engagement and resolve to advance development in the State to a great extent, and there are several challenges encountered by youth leveraging social media to foster development in Delta State. The study recommends that social media activists should endeavor to collaborate with community leaders and relevant authorities to promote community engagement and development of policies to improve the wellbeing of the people, among others.

Keywords: *Development, Social Media, Activism and Youth Commitment.*

Suggested citation: Okoli, A.N., & Ulo, E. (2025). Harnessing Social Media Activism: A Focus on Youth Commitment to Development in Delta State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Innovative Studies and Sustainability*, 1(3), 212-222. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1\(3\).17](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1(3).17)

Introduction

Contemporarily, patterns of people's interactions, communication and mobilization around social causes have been largely revolutionized by social media as a result of the global preponderance of social media - cutting across the boundaries of countries across the development spectrum (Neag, Supa & Mihailidis, 2024). Many people have incorporated social media usage into their daily life. As social media continues to grow rapidly and penetrate different spheres of human endeavor, the mode and pattern of information transmission are becoming largely influenced by social media. Social media encompasses a range of digital platforms that enable information to be rapidly transmitted digitally among users. According to Allcott and Gentzkow (2017), information dissemination has been transformed by social media platforms like WhatsApp, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, etc. Virality is a common feature of the social media phenomena that stimulates people to use them. The virality of social media is unparalleled in its ability to

propel issues and people to widespread attention. This is however a function of the easy, seamless and rapid information transmission that is associated with them (Teh, Huah& Si, 2014).

Basically all forms of messages can be transmitted via social media platforms. These include audios, pictures, videos, audiovisuals and documents, among others. It must be stated however that not all social media platforms accommodate all the forms of messages enumerated hereinbefore (Ufuophu-Biri&Ojoboh, 2017). Also, the level of censorship on messages sent through social media is in most cases limited to the rules and regulations of the platform concerned and not to a specific country's administration. For instance, X's terms of service govern the content Nigerians can post, independent of federal or state regulations. This creates a possibility for online to cover a wide range of themes and issues in their message transmission (Boulianne & Theocharis, 2020; Torres, Gerhart&Negahban, 2018).

Contemporarily, deployment of social media for addressing social issues emerged as a preponderant phenomenon across the globe. The rationale behind its preponderance is not far from social media's popularity, widespread coverage, and ease of use. In a country like Nigeria, where young people constitute the largest demographic, leveraging social media for information dissemination is a preponderant phenomenon. And since the country still grapples with a myriad of developmental problems such as poverty, unemployment, inequality, inadequate infrastructure and political instability, among others, harnessing social media's potential for youth activism and engagement has become inevitable. The emergence of social media activism as an innovative approach to addressing the issues in the society stems from the limited impact of traditional approaches on youth engagement and development. Social media empowers young people to spread awareness, mobilize support, and drive change on critical issues affecting their society. Apparently, the surge in leveraging social media for activism in Nigeria warrants a thorough investigation of its impact, challenges, and potential, hence, the conduct of this research.

Statement of the Problem

Social media's preponderance in Nigeria has amplified discussions about the challenges facing the youth given the abundance of information. Since the traditional modes of engagement have yielded limited results in the aspect of addressing the prevailing hardships, it is imperative to harness social media activism as a mechanism for the mobilization of youth in Delta State toward meaningful participation in the process of development (Madueke *et al.*, 2017). A significant feature of Nigeria's leadership structure is the overwhelming dominance of leadership positions by the older generations, leading many to opine that a critical issue hindering Nigeria's development is the underwhelming youth representation in governance and decision-making processes. This phenomenon has further been exacerbated by the ineffective utilization of social media platforms for activism purposes (Abdul *et al.*, 2018). According to Erubami (2020), although social media has revolutionized information dissemination and mobilization globally, its consequence for youth engagement in Delta State remains understudied. It must be stated that a significant knowledge gap exists in understanding how social media fosters youth engagement in development. There has been a focus on how offline activism promotes youth engagement in previous studies, while ignoring the potential of social media as a force for creating awareness on public concerns and driving development. Furthermore, there is limited empirical evidence on successful social media-driven development initiatives in Delta State. Hence, the study was organized to assess social media activism's effectiveness in fostering youth commitment to development.

Research Objectives

The study specifically aimed to:

1. Find out the current state of social media activism among youth in Delta State;
2. Examine how effective social media activism among youth can foster development initiatives in Delta State. and
3. Ascertain the challenges youth encounter in using social media activism for development in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following questions were posed to guide the study:

1. What is the current state of social media activism among youth in Delta State?
2. How effective social media activism among youth can foster development initiatives in Delta State?
3. What are the challenges youth encounter in using social media activism for development in Delta State?

State of Social Media Activism in Nigeria

Umegbolu (2020) opined that over the past decade, social media activism in Nigeria has experienced significant growth and evolution, metamorphosing into a powerful tool for the mobilization of citizens, influencing public opinion, and social change advocacy. An upward trend has been noted in internet penetration over the years in the Nigerian social media landscape, with about 43% of the population having access to the internet and over a 100 million active social media users, with X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp being the dominant platforms (The Competence Centre on Foresight, 2018; Guizzardi *et al.*, 2016). The increase in social media usage stems from the increased mobile phone accessibility and adoption by a large demographic. This growing social media usage has been vital for advocating for changes in the Nigerian society as disseminated information has the capacity to reach numerous people (Husain *et al.*, 2014). The main social media types are shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Data of Worldwide Social Media Users in Millions

Source: <http://www.statista.com>

Over the years, occurrences like the abduction of the Chibok girls, Lekki Toll Gate shootings, SARS brutality, election malpractices, etc., have facilitated social media trends, especially on X (formerly Twitter). These have created hashtags like #EndPoliceBrutalityinNigeria, #BringBackOurGirls, #LekkiTollGateShooting, etc (Erubami, 2020). According to Adenrele and Olugbenga (2014), incidents of unintended harm, interpersonal violence, unlawful detention, abductions, politicians' impunity, ethnic

discrimination, political disenfranchisements, sexual abuse, unemployment, corruption, hike in tuition fees, police brutality and social exclusion are have all been largely posted by social media activists for their audience to engage with and draw the attention of relevant authorities to take actions.

A pioneering social media initiative was the protests against the removal of fuel subsidy by the Federal Government in 2012 under the hashtag #OccupyNigeria. This was followed by the movement demanding the release of the Chibok schoolgirls kidnapped by terrorists under the hashtag #BringBackOurGirls. In 2017, the #NotTooYoungToRun campaign began on social media campaign to advocate for increased youth political participation. This was done to raise awareness on the lack of young people in political offices in Nigeria. In 2020, the nationwide protest against police brutality started in Ughelli, Delta State and sparked the #EndSARS trend on social media. Most recently, in July 2024, the #EndHungerProtest and #RevolutionNow campaigns trended on social media subsequently leading to a series of nationwide protests in August. These social media campaigns were done to amplify the voices of those that were being marginalized, demand accountability from public officials, foster conversations on critical issues on a national, continental and global levels, mobilize resources and promotion of social justice, etc (Ufuophu-Biri&Ojoboh, 2017).

Social Media Activism and Youth Commitment to Development

Social media's growing influence has dramatically revolutionized the way young people engage with social issues, mobilize, and advocate for change (Ahmad, Alvi and Ittefaq, 2019). In Delta State, internet access has facilitated youth engagement, empowering them to drive development and promote social justice. Social media's ability to transcend geographical boundaries, enabled the youth to engage in local and national conversations and by so doing, amplifying the voices of youth in Delta State to express opinions and share experiences (Chiamogu et al.,2021). Over the years, many individuals have taken utilized the wide array of real-time information to make informed decisions and take necessary actions. Apart from raising awareness on critical issues and promoting informed engagement, Anyim (2021) purports that mobilization of resources, support, and action for development causes and build connections with like-minded individuals (promoting collective action) are facilitated by social media.

Social media impact studies in regards to youth advocacy abound like #EndSARS, #NotTooYoungToRun, #BringBackOurGirls, #EndHungerProtest and #RevolutionNow, etc. These instances show how social media activism facilitated youth engagement and commitment to development. This is because many of these campaigns first started as conversations on social media platforms, especially X, and after the issues discussed garnered attention, they transcended into real life actions. It must be stated that some of the issues addressed on social media has prompted relevant authorities to take necessary actions such as the dissolution of SARS after the nationwide protest (Uwazuruike, 2020).

Challenges to Youth Social Media Activism

Despite the numerous benefits of adopting social media for activism, some associated challenges are capable of inhibiting its effectiveness. While there is an abundance of information on social media, spreading fake news and misinformation is an attendant challenge. X, for example, does not effectively regulate the information disseminated by individuals has amplified the presence of fake news which causes unnecessary panic and rage among users of these platforms (Uldam, 2017). This was why the Nigerian government banned Twitter from around June 2021 to January 2022 citing that fake news and misinformation have instigated real-world violence and undermined the corporate existence of the country. For Caron (2017), incidences of online harassment, bullying and intimidation from individuals that disagree with the messages that are posted by activists occur frequently to suppress the voices of these activists and prevent them from carrying out their activities. Government censorship and regulation which is mainly seen in countries like China, North Korea, etc, is another obstacle (Ahmad, Alvi&Ittefaq, 2019). This was also attempted by the Nigerian government when Twitter was banned in 2021. Furthermore, there is also the challenge of limited internet accessibility and affordability, poor network

connectivity and infrastructure, and inadequate digital literacy skills. All of these may inhibited the effectiveness of the messages passed by activists and limit offline mobilization and sustainability.

Theoretical Framework: Technological Frame of Reference Theory

The technological frame of reference theory was propounded in 1994 by Wanda Orlikowski and Debra Gash. The theory enunciated the impact that individual or group differences have on the overall perception of an existing technology. According to Erubami (2020), the theory purported that people's technologies and how they relate to them is a product of the variations in their perceived efficiency and relevance. Hence, those who view a given technology as very efficient and relevant to a particular course will actively use that technology to pursue such a course. In general, through interactions and experiences with technology, people develop a mental frame of the applicability and usefulness of this technology to different spheres of endeavor. It is this mental frame that subsequently guides their impression of the practicalities of the given technology and its application in a given sphere of endeavor. Based on this theory, it is clear that youth in Delta State who perceive the usefulness of social media deployment for activism, will use it for promoting development causes. Therefore, those who have good experiences of social media being effectively used to address social issues will have positive assumptions about them and ultimately encourage the adoption of social media for activism purposes.

Methodology

The study employed a cross-sectional design, as it facilitated data collection from several respondents on the subject; 'Harnessing Social Media Activism: A Focus on Youth Commitment to Development in Delta State, Nigeria'. 392 respondents from Asaba Metropolis were chosen for the study through the purposive sampling technique. This limited participation to only individuals that are knowledgeable about social media were involved in the study. A structured questionnaire titled "*Social Media Activism and Youth Commitment to Development in Delta State*" was designed for the study. The questionnaire contained Parts I, II and II to reflect the three research objectives and comprised 14 closed-ended questions derived from the themes of the objectives. The questionnaire's validity was determined by subjecting it to face and content validity tests, and the reliability was determined using the Cronbach's Alpha reliability test. This generated a reliability coefficient of ≥ 82 implies high reliability. Lastly, data collected were analysed using simple percentages, arithmetic mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the current state of social media activism among youth in Delta State?

Table 1. Most Used Social Media Platforms

S/N	Question	Facebook	X	Instagram	LinkedIn	TikTok	YouTube
1	Which social media platforms do you actively use for your social media activism?	73 (18.6%)	114 (29.1%)	93 (23.7%)	36 (9.2%)	34 (8.7%)	42 (10.7%)
2	Which social media platform(s) do you think is most effective for reaching the target audience and promoting development-related contents?	67 (17.1%)	132 (33.7%)	73 (18.6%)	39 (10%)	46 (11.7%)	35 (8.9%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 2. Frequency of Social Media Usage for Activism

S/N	Question	Daily	Bi-weekly	Weekly	Monthly	Never
1	What is your frequency of using social media for activism purposes?	187 (44.7%)	93 (23.7%)	42 (10.7%)	36 (9.2%)	34 (8.7%)
2	How frequent do you see social, economic, government and development-related content on social media?	199 (50.8%)	73 (18.6%)	46 (11.7%)	39 (10%)	35 (8.9%)
		Education	Healthcare	Governance	Environmental Issues	Human Rights
3	What social cause do you advocate mostly for online?	42 (10.7%)	34 (8.7%)	187 (44.7%)	36 (9.2%)	93 (23.7%)
		Sharing Posts	Commenting on Posts	Creating Original Contents	Participating Online Discussions	Donating to Causes
4	How do you engage in social media activism?	122 (31.1%)	130 (33.2%)	76 (19.4%)	31 (7.9%)	33 (8.4%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 1 above shows 73 (18.6%) of the respondents actively used Facebook for social media activism, 114 (29.1%) actively used X for social media activism, 93 (23.7%) actively used Instagram for social media activism, 36 (9.2%) used LinkedIn for social media activism, 34 (8.7%) used TikTok for social media activism, and 42 (10.7%) used YouTube for social media activism. Also, 67 (17.1%) of thought Facebook to be the most effective social media platform for reaching the target audience and promoting development-related contents, 132 (33.7%) thought X to be the most effective social media platform for reaching the target audience and promoting development-related contents, 73 (18.6%) thought Instagram to be the most effective social media platform for reaching the target audience and development-related contents, 39 (10.0%) thought LinkedIn to be the most effective social media platform for reaching the target audience and development-related contents, 46 (11.7%) thought TikTok to be the most effective social media platform for reaching the target audience and promoting development-related contents, and 35 (8.9%) thought Youtube to be the most effective social media platform for reaching the target audience and promoting development-related contents.

Table 2 shows that 187 (44.7%) of the respondents used social media for activism purposes daily, 93 (23.7%) actively used social media for activism purposes on a bi-weekly basis, 42 (10.7%) used social media for activism purposes on a weekly basis, 36 (9.2%) used social media for activism purposes on a monthly basis and 34 (8.7%) did not use social media for activism purposes. Also, 199 (50.8%) saw activism-related contents on social media on a daily basis, 73 (18.6%) saw activism-related contents on social media on a bi-weekly basis, 46 (11.7%) saw activism-related contents on social media on a weekly basis, 39 (10.0%) of the respondents saw activism-related contents on social media on a monthly basis and 35 (8.9%) never saw activism-related contents on social media. It can also be seen that 42 (10.7%) said that they use social media to advocate for educational causes, 34 (8.7%) said that they use social media to advocate for healthcare causes, 187 (44.7%) said that they use social media to advocate for governance causes, 36 (9.2%) said that they use social media to advocate for environmental causes and 93 (23.7%) said that they use social media to advocate for human rights causes. Lastly, 122 (31.1%) reported that they engaged in social media activism by sharing posts, 130 (33.2%) reported that they engaged in social media activism by commenting on posts, 76 (19.4%) reported that they engaged in social media activism by creating original contents, 31 (7.9%) reported that they engaged in social media activism by participating in online discussions and 33 (8.4%) reported that they engaged in social media activism by donating to causes.

Research Question 2

How effective social media activism among youth can foster development initiatives in Delta State?

Table 3. Analysis of Research Question 2

S/N	Statement	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Have you ever attended an offline event or protest related to an online campaign?	3.94	0.78	Accepted
2	Social media activism has been effective in addressing several development issues in Delta State	3.54	1.12	Accepted
3	Social media activism has facilitated resource mobilization for certain developmental causes in Delta State	3.90	0.83	Accepted
4	Through social media posts, a lot of people have become more aware of the developmental challenges in Delta State and are ready to take the needed action	3.80	0.88	Accepted
5	Social media activism sometimes facilitates community engagement and collective action to address developmental issues	2.87	1.63	Rejected

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 3 shows the opinion of respondents on the effectiveness of youth social media activism in fostering development initiatives in Delta State. They accepted that they have attended an offline event or protest related to an online campaign in Delta state (with a Mean of 3.94 and Standard Deviation of 0.78), social media activism has been effective in addressing several development issues in Delta State (with a Mean of 3.54 and Standard Deviation of 1.12), social media activism has facilitated resource mobilization for certain developmental causes in Delta State (with a Mean of 3.90 and Standard Deviation of 0.83), through social media posts, a lot of people have become more aware of the developmental challenges in Delta State and are ready to take the needed action (with a Mean of 3.80 and Standard Deviation of 0.88). They, however, rejected that social media activism sometimes facilitates community engagement and collective action to address developmental issues (with a Mean of 2.87 and Standard Deviation of 1.63).

Research Question 3

What are the challenges youth encounter in using social media activism for development in Delta State?

Table 4. Analysis of Research Question 3

S/N	Statement	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	You have experienced online harassment or bullying for airing your views	3.76	0.91	Accepted
2	You have been arrested or invited for questioning by law enforcement agencies over a post(s) you made on social media	4.04	0.71	Accepted
3	You have faced censorship or content restrictions on social media when making activism-related posts	2.61	1.20	Rejected
4	You sometimes lack funds to facilitate your activism efforts on social media	3.03	1.01	Accepted
5	Occasional poor network connection and frequent power outages inhibit your use of social media for development purposes	3.54	1.01	Accepted

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 shows the opinion of respondents on the challenges encountered by the youth in using social media for development purposes in Delta State. They accepted that they have experienced online harassment or bullying for airing their views on social issues (with a Mean of 3.76 and Standard Deviation of 0.91), been arrested or invited for questioning by law enforcement agencies over a post(s) they have made on social media (with a Mean of 4.04 and Standard Deviation of 0.71), sometimes lack funds to

facilitate their activism efforts on social media (with a Mean of 3.03 and Standard Deviation of 1.01) and occasional poor network connection and frequent power outages inhibit their use of social media for development purposes (with a Mean of 3.54 and Standard Deviation of 1.01). They, however, rejected that they faced censorship or content restrictions on social media when making activism-related posts (with a Mean of 2.61 and Standard Deviation of 1.20).

Discussion of Findings

Firstly, the data analysis revealed the current state of social media activism among youth in Delta State. The analysis shows that the youth actively use Facebook, X, Instagram and YouTube, among others for social media activism. It was discovered, however, that X is the most used social media platform for activism among youth in Delta State. Also, X has been regarded as the most effective social media platform for reaching the target audience and promoting social, economic, government and development-related contents. This is followed by Instagram and Facebook social media platforms. This implies that contents driven on X are expected to be more effective in addressing developmental problems in the society. It was also discovered that a lot of youth use social media for activism purposes daily as well as on a bi-weekly basis. Also, many respondents saw activism-related contents on social media on a daily basis. This implies that there is adequate circulation of activists' contents on social media platforms. The different causes advocated for on social media platforms include education, healthcare, governance, environment and human rights. Lastly, the different modes of social media activism included sharing posts, commenting on posts, creating original contents, participating in online discussions and donating to causes. This finding supports those of Erubami (2020) and Ufuophu-Biri and Ojoboh (2017) that social media has transformed the mode of information dissemination and has become a powerful tool for addressing social issues in the society.

Secondly, the analysis shows that social media activism has impacted youth engagement and commitment to development in Delta State to a great extent. As part of the activism process, several individuals have attended an offline event or protest related to an online campaign in Delta State. Some protests that have taken place over the years were instigated by social media discourse and campaigns. Also, social media activism has been effective in addressing several development issues and facilitated resource mobilization for certain developmental causes in Delta State. It must be stated that through social media posts, a lot of people have become more aware of the developmental challenges in Delta State and are ready to take the needed action. However, it has been reported that social media activism has not been effective in facilitating community engagement and collective action to address developmental issues. This is corroborated by Umegbolu (2020) and Uwazuruike (2020) who opined that social media activism was fundamental to the organization of the "End SARS Protest" in Nigeria in 2020.

Lastly, the analysis revealed that there are several challenges encountered by youth in using social media for development purposes in Delta State. One of the major challenges facing youth engaging in online social media activism is online harassment or bullying. The fact is many individuals are often harassed and bullied for airing their views on social issues or clamoring for a change to policies are detrimental to the wellbeing of the members of the society. Similarly, some activists have been arrested or invited for questioning by law enforcement agencies over a post(s) they have made on social media as a way of suppressing their voices and curtailing their activities. Like other endeavors, social media activism requires funding and sometimes youth activists lack funds to facilitate their activism efforts on social media and occasionally, poor network connection and frequent power outages inhibit their use of social media for development purposes. Interestingly, censorship or content restrictions on social media when making activism-related posts have been reported to not be a major challenge for activists. This is mainly because social media is owned and managed by foreign companies that are not controlled by the Nigerian government. This is in line with the findings of Caron (2017) who reported several incidences of online

harassment, bullying and intimidation from individuals who disagree with the messages that are posted on social media.

Conclusion

Social media is a powerful tool for creating awareness about issues that negatively impact the lives of people in society and promoting development initiatives effectively. This is why in Delta State, many youth use social media platforms for activism purposes. This is done to create awareness on issues like poverty, unemployment, inequality, human rights violations, corruption, electoral malpractices, etc. These issues cut across education, social, economic, healthcare and governance. Social media activism is done through sharing posts, commenting on posts, creating original contents, participating in online discussions and donating to causes. In Delta State, social media activism has impacted youth engagement and commitment to development which is seen in the attendance of offline events or protests related to online campaigns, resource mobilization for certain developmental causes and increased social awareness. However, this has not translated into significant community engagement and fundamental policy changes to improve the lives of individuals across communities in Delta State. In the process of engaging in online activism, several challenges are encountered by youth such as online harassment or bullying, intimidation, arrest or invitation for questioning by law enforcement agencies over a post(s) were made on social media, lack of funding and poor network connection and frequent power outages which inhibit the effective use of social media for development purposes. It must be stated that if these issues are not addressed, they may hinder the social media activism in Delta State and by extension, inhibit the development of the State.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. Social media activists should endeavor to collaborate with community leaders and relevant authorities to promote community engagement and development of policies to improve the wellbeing of the people.
2. The government should establish an agency to take cognizance and evaluate the information provided by social media activists to enable them address the different issues that are raised.
3. Social media platforms, security officials and other relevant agencies should make efforts to curtail cyber-bullying and harassment to encourage the activities of activists online. There should be an establishment of mechanisms for monitoring and reporting social media abuse and hate speech related to activism issues.
4. There should be an establishment of feedback mechanisms that allow the public to provide input on activists' priorities and initiatives. This ensures that advocacy efforts align with the genuine concerns of the community.

References

- Abdul, S. D., Alamai, M. M., Musa, A., & Halilu, B. I. (2018). Social media and political participation: Is Facebook democratizing our youth in Nigeria? *International Journal of Operational Research in Management, Social Sciences & Education*, 4(1), 108–126.
- Adenrele, A. R., & Olugbenga, O. M. (2014). Challenges of human rights abuses in Nigerian democratic governance – which way forward? *Journal of Social Economics Research*, 1(5), 87–96.

- Ahmad, T., Alvi, A., & Ittefaq, M. (2019). The use of social media on political participation among university students: An analysis of survey results from rural Pakistan. *SAGE Open*, 9(3), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019864484>
- Allcott, H., & Gentzkow, M. (2017). Social media and fake news in the 2016 election. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 31(2), 211–236. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.31.2.211>
- Anyim, W. O. (2021). Twitter ban in Nigeria: Implications on economy, freedom of speech and information sharing. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 5975. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5975/>
- Boulianne, S., & Theocharis, Y. (2020). Young people, digital media, and engagement: A meta-analysis of research. *Social Science Computer Review*, 38(2), 111–127. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894439318814190>
- Caron, C. (2017). Speaking up about bullying on YouTube: Teenagers' vlogs as civic engagement. *Canadian Journal of Communication*, 42(4), 645–668. <https://doi.org/10.22230/cjc.2017v42n4a3156>
- Chiamogu, A. P., Obikeze, O. S. A., Chiamogu, U. P., & Odikpo, E. (2021). Social media and group consciousness in Nigeria: Appraising the prevalence of socio-political protests. *Open Journal of Political Science*, 11(4), 682–696. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojps.2021.114043>
- Erubami, J. A. (2020). Public perception of social media contributions to political participation processes in Delta State, Nigeria. *Acta Universitatis Danubius. Communicatio*, 14(1). Retrieved from <https://dj.univ-danubius.ro/index.php/AUDC/article/view/400>
- Guizzardi, A., Monti, A., & Ranieri, E. (2016). Rating hotel quality for corporate business travel departments. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(12), 2842–2863. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-07-2015-0350>
- Husain, R., Alsamydai, J. M., Alnawas, A. I., & Yousif, A. R. (2014). The impact of marketing innovation on creating sustainable competitive advantage: The case of private commercial banks in Jordan. *Asian Journal of Marketing*, 4(3), 113–130.
- Madueke, O., Nwosu, C., Ogbonnaya, C., Anumadu, A., & Okeke, V. O. S. (2017). The role of social media in enhancing political participation in Nigeria. *IDOSR Journal of Arts and Management*, 2(3), 44–54.
- Neag, A., Supa, M., & Mihailidis, P. (2024). Researching social media and activism with children and youth: A scoping review. *International Journal of Communication*, 18, 2107–2128. Retrieved from <https://ijoc.org/index.php/ijoc/article/view/21717>
- Teh, P. L., Huah, L. P., & Si, Y. W. (2014). The intention to share and re-shared among the young adults towards a posting at social networking sites. In Á. Rocha, A. M. Correia, F. B. Tan, & K. A. Stroetmann (Eds.), *New Perspectives in Information Systems and Technologies, Volume 1* (pp. 13–21). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05951-8_2
- The Competence Centre on Foresight. (2018). Number of social media users worldwide 2010–17 with forecasts to 2021. European Commission. Retrieved from https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/visualisation/number-social-media-users-worldwide-2010-17-forecasts-2021_en
- Torres, R. R., Gerhart, N., & Negahban, A. (2018). Combating fake news: An investigation of information verification behaviors on social networking sites. In *Proceedings of the 51st Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences* (pp. 3976–3985). <https://doi.org/10.24251/HICSS.2018.499>
- Ufuophu-Biri, E., & Ojoboh, L. O. (2017). Social media as a tool for political resistance: Lessons from the Arab Spring and the Nigerian protests. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 6(1), 61–66. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ajis-2017-0006>

- Uldam, J. (2017). Social media visibility: Challenges to activism. *Media, Culture & Society*, 40(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443717726003>
- Umegbolu, C. (2020). End SARS: A revolution by the people for the people on police brutality in Nigeria. [Unpublished manuscript].
- Uwazuruike, A. R. (2020). #EndSARS: The movement against police brutality in Nigeria. *Harvard Human Rights Journal*. Retrieved from <http://clerk.uclan.ac.uk/35527/3/35527%20EndSars%20%281%29.pdf>
- Zuleika, P., & Legiran, T. (2022). Cross-sectional study as research design in medicine. *Archives of the Medicine and Case Reports*, 3(2), 256–259.